

Clinical Image

Large dentigerous cyst associated with an impacted mandibular canine

Georges Aoun

- Dean of the Faculty of Dental Medicine, Lebanese University, Beirut, Lebanon
- Full Professor of Oral Medicine, Faculty of Dental Medicine, Lebanese University

Corresponding author: Professor Georges Aoun; e-mail: dr.georgesoun@gmail.com

Background

Dentigerous cysts (DCs) are developmental odontogenic cysts associated with impacted

teeth. They are generally asymptomatic and the majority of the cases are fortuitously detected on conventional imaging techniques used in dental practice such as panoramic radiographs. In decreasing order, DCs are most frequently associated with mandibular third molar, maxillary canine, mandibular premolar, and maxillary third molar. Mandibular canines are less commonly affected. This "clinical image" presents a large DC associated with an impacted mandibular canine.

Case presentation

A healthy 35-year-old male presented for a dental check-up. On a panoramic radiograph, a well-defined radiolucency, in the anterior region of the mandible, extending horizontally from the root of tooth #34 to the apical region of tooth #45, and vertically from the upper third of the alveolar bone to the lower border of the mandible, centered on impacted left mandibular canine (#33). Borders are scalloped and roots of teeth #73 and #32 to #44 are involved in the lesion (Figure 1). A presumed diagnosis of a DC was made at this point based on the radiographic appearance.

Further radiological investigations (three-dimensional imaging / CBCT) are scheduled in order to elaborate the adequate treatment plan.

Figure 1: Digital panoramic radiograph showing a large cyst (red arrows) associated with the permanent impacted left mandibular canine